

THE CONTRIBUTION OF THE ENERGY INDUSTRY TO SOCIETY'S ECONOMIC GROWTH

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Abstract: Energy and energy resources are one of the factors that ensure the stable development of the economy of any country, determine the level of its socio-economic development and the well-being of its population. According to experts and scientists, the existing natural fuel and energy resources (natural gas, oil) found in the world are sufficient for use for 60-150 years. For this reason, policies to ensure energy security and improve energy efficiency are being implemented in many countries.

Key words: Economy, energy resources, development, fuel-energy, energy security, power plants, renewable energy.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the energy sector is the basis of the development of any country. Opportunities for economic development, comfortable living of the population, education, medical services, social security, moderate activity of communal economy are created in this area. But today, it is difficult to keep the huge energy infrastructure in working order, and increase the volume of electricity production without moving the industry to the path of market economy. The goals can be achieved only with the help of the most modern achievements in the construction and operation of power plants, power grids and alternative energy infrastructure. Development of energy based on the laws of the market creates conditions for competition, which allows attracting the most qualified engineers with modern

experience and technologies to the implementation of projects. At the same time, it is possible to introduce equipment and methods that will be relevant for ten years to the energy industry of Uzbekistan.

One of the successful steps towards the transition to market relations in the energy sector is the implementation of energy production projects, including renewable energy sources, on the basis of public-private partnership, a completely new model for Uzbekistan. Today, this model has become the basis for all under construction and planned power plants. Thus, the commissioning of new power plants, including thermal, solar photoelectric, wind power plants can be an example of market changes taking place in the country's energy sector.

Public-private partnership projects are conducted on the basis of a tender, that is, a competitive market. In this regard, the International Finance Corporation, the Asian Development Bank, and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, which are part of the World Bank Group, are providing technical support for the adoption of the best international experience and conducting tenders. It should be noted that the winner of the tender is responsible for the design, construction and operation of the new power plant. A long-term agreement for 20-25 years will be concluded with it regarding the purchase of electricity produced. A profitable price offer (tariff) for electricity is considered the main criterion for winning the tender. But before submitting their offer, the tender participants must go through the qualifying stage. In this, they must prove their high experience, availability of funds, ability to implement and provide such projects. Thus, market principles, which have been intensively implemented in the energy sector of Uzbekistan for the past 3 years, allow creating healthy competition in this field, and the interest of independent producers of electricity is a proof of this.

METHOD AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

In recent years, fundamental changes aimed at developing the economy and improving the lifestyle of the population have been implemented in our country. Free economic zones, technological parks, and clusters are being established in

various regions of the republic. On the basis of such strategic programs as "A prosperous village", "A prosperous neighborhood", "Safe city" huge creative works are being done in cities and villages, which are completely renewing their image. Accordingly, tourism is also developing. In turn, more attention is being paid to the issue of environmental protection and ecological stability than ever before.

Currently, the length of power lines of energy systems in our country is 254,8 thousand kilometers. Of these, 218,400 kilometers are low-voltage distribution networks with a voltage of 0.4-10 kV. 62.4% of them have been used for more than 30 years. The distribution networks are very outdated, which leads to a significant loss of electricity. That is, at the same time, 20 percent of the total electricity output from thermal power plants to the electricity grid is being lost. Just imagine: one-fifth of the light and heat source produced for us is flying into the air.

It is necessary to pay attention to the following in order to eliminate such defects, eliminate defects and avoid waste.

- modernization of energy devices of thermal power plants (40 percent), renewal of electrical systems intended for the supply and distribution of electricity (57 percent), transformer points (52 percent) and substations (21 percent);
- commissioning of new generator capacities (which will increase electricity production by 20-40 percent);
- scheduled maintenance from time to time to keep existing energy equipment in working condition...

It is clear that these good and important things cannot be done by themselves and easily. That is, it will require a lot of money, strong will, tireless work and the support of the people. That is why, in the relevant decision of the government, in order to modernize the energy systems of the republic, to install new, economical ones instead of high-cost devices, in addition to the own funds of "Uzbekenergo" JSC, international financial institutions and the Development and Reconstruction Fund of Uzbekistan It was determined that the bonds of the army will also be directed.

The issue of improving energy efficiency in socio-economic areas is the focus of the government's attention today. According to experts, the energy capacity of the national economy is 2-2.5 times higher than that of developed countries.

If about 23% of energy consumption in the world falls on the housing sector, in Uzbekistan this number is 40%. In particular, in Europe, energy consumption per 1 square meter is 120-150 kilowatt-hours per year, while in Uzbekistan this indicator exceeds 390 kilowatt-hours.

1352.4 mln. in 2020 in exchange for implementation of organizational and technical measures in economic sectors in the process of carrying out work on increasing energy efficiency. cubic meters of natural gas, 917.5 mln. kilowatt-hours of electricity savings have been achieved.

CONCLUSION

Renewable energy projects implemented in Uzbekistan contribute to the implementation of the tasks set before the country's energy sector. It also helps to reduce annual greenhouse gas emissions by approximately 500,000 tons of CO₂ equivalent.

Thus, based on numbers and evidence, it can be said that in the last few years, significant progress has been made in the development of Uzbekistan's energy industry based on the best international experience, and in ensuring that the energy sector operates in the conditions of market relations. All of this will meet growing consumer demands and provide an opportunity to ensure the energy security of the country in the current and future periods.

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